

Evaluation of selected third International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery (1977) entries to brown planthopper and ragged stunt. IRRI, wet season, 1977.

Variety ^a	BPH count/hill ^b 70 DT	Ragged stunt (%)	BPH damage rating ^c 80 DT	Resistance to BPH biotypes ^d in greenhouse		
				1	2	3
B2360-11-3-2-3	118	100	5	R	S	R
Chianung sen yu 19	279	90	7	R	S	S
CR94-13	60	79	3	R	R	S
CR179-1-717	56	72	5	R	R	S
IR2307-72-2-2-1	65	75	7	R	S	R
Taichung sen yu 204	57	98	7	R	S	S
Triveni	36	61	5	S	S	S
ARC 6650	37	96	7	R	R	S
Babawee	9	29	1	R	R	R
Balamawee	33	8	1	R	R	R
Gangala	29	28	1	R	R	R
Heendoramawee	15	58	1	R	R	S
Hondarawala	30	34	1	R	R	R
Lekam Samba	100	13	1	R	R	R
Muthumanikam	160	23	1	R	R	R
PTB19	56	7	1	R	R	R
PTB21	38	0	1	R	R	R
PTB33	48	0	1	R	R	R
Rathu Heenati	37	19	1	R	R	R
Sinna Sivappu	14	4	1	R	R	R
Sudu Hondarawala	44	56	1	R	R	R
Thirissa	16	59	1	R	R	R
Suduru Samba	69	31	1	R	R	R
ASD 7	58	61	5	R	R	S
Mudgo	238	76	7	R	S	R
TN1	121	100	9	S	S	S

^a Field study replicated four times. Four border rows of IR19173-17 planted at ends of test entry rows and two rows planted between each test entry. Plot size of test entries was 1 m² and consisted of four rows of four plants each, spaced at 25 × 25 cm.

^b Collected with a D-Vac suction machine. All BPH adults at 30 days after transplanting (DT) and mostly nymphs at 70 DT.

^c Based on the Standard Evaluation System for rice: 1 = no damage; 9 = plants dead.

^d R = resistant; S = susceptible.

PTB21, PTB33, and Sinna Sivappu, all of which have high resistance to the three biotypes in greenhouse studies, had the lowest BPH damage rating and the least ragged stunt (see table). Because of the small plots and high BPH populations in the susceptible border rows, hoppers were abundant even on resistant varieties at 70 days after transplanting. Varieties that were susceptible to biotype 2 generally had a high incidence of ragged stunt. It was not determined whether resistance to the vector or resistance to the disease, or both, caused the low ragged stunt incidence in certain varieties.

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Allelic relationships among four genes for BP13 resistance

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Three years after the rice variety IR26 was released, its resistance to the brown planthopper (BPH) broke down. Several breeding strategies for the control of BPH have since been suggested. At the international symposium on BPH held at IRRI in 1977, four strategies were proposed: 1) sequential release, 2) pyramiding the major genes, 3) multiline varieties, and 4) horizontal resistance.

In combining two or more resistance

genes, the allelic relationships among the four known resistance genes must be determined. We made crosses among the four resistant cultivars Mudgo, ASD7, Rathu Heenati, and Babawee, representing *Bph 1*, *bph 2*, *Bph 3*, and *bph 4* genes, respectively. Then the F₂ and B₁F₁ populations from each cross were analyzed by the bulk seedling test, using BPH biotype 1.

Results indicate that 1) *bph 2*, as well as *Bph 1*, segregates independently of both *Bph 3* and *bph 4*; 2) not only *Bph 1* and *bph 2* are either allelic or closely linked, *Bph 3* and *bph 4* are also closely linked.

According to the results, we may be able to combine *Bph 1* with *Bph 3*, *Bph 1*

with *bph 4*, *bph 2* with *Bph 3*, or *bph 2* with *bph 4* in a cultivar. On the other hand, it may be difficult to combine *Bph 1* with *bph 2*, or *Bph 3* with *bph 4*.

According to Lakshiminarayana and Khush (1977), PTB 21 has one dominant and one recessive gene, and one of them is either *Bph 1* or *bph 2*.

To identify the other gene of PTB 21, the cultivar was crossed with Rathu Heenati and Babawee. No susceptible plants were observed in the F₂ populations of either cross. It appears that the other gene of PTB 21 is either *Bph 3* or *bph 4*. It may be concluded that the resistance in PTB 21 is controlled by either *Bph 1* and *bph 4*, or *bph 2* and *Bph 3* gene pairs.